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Proteomic Analysis Reveals Accompanying Anion-Dependent Changes of Cadmium Toxicity During *Arabidopsis thaliana* Development

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ABSTRACT

Cadmium (Cd) is a significant environmental pollutant with widespread detrimental effects on living organisms, making it a frequent subject of laboratory studies. However, different types of Cd salts are used to spike media, often without considering the possibility that accompanying anions may influence the effects of metal cations. Using two commonly used Cd salts, CdSO₄ and CdCl₂, we observed distinct toxicity effects on *Arabidopsis thaliana* development. On a physiological level, 7-day-old seedlings exposed to 50 μM CdSO₄ had shorter roots than those treated with CdCl₂. Proteomic analysis revealed strong downregulation of proteins involved in microtubule organization and primary cell wall synthesis in the root of plants exposed to CdSO₄. Additionally, these plants exhibited higher Cd uptake from the medium and greater Cd accumulation in the shoot, indicating that the SO₄²⁻, as an accompanying anion, exacerbates Cd toxicity. These findings highlight the critical but often overlooked role of accompanying anions in modulating the toxic effects of heavy metals on plants.

1 | Introduction

Cadmium (Cd) represents one of the trace metals that pose a danger to human and animal health due to its potential for accumulation in the food chain and high environmental mobility. Its detrimental effects on plant physiology, morphology and metabolism—such as growth inhibition, nutrient deficiencies and inhibition of fundamental metabolic pathways like nitrogen metabolism or photosynthesis—make Cd a critical global and local food security risk factor (reviewed in Haider et al. 2021). In some countries, such as China, Cd contamination has been on the rise in agricultural soils (Shi et al. 2019; Wen et al. 2022).

Under laboratory conditions, Cd stress is often simulated by spiking the growth medium with Cd salts, typically CdCl₂,

CdSO₄ or Cd(NO₃)₂ (Haider et al. 2021). The applied concentrations vary between studies, ranging from nano- to millimolar scales; however, the upper range represents concentrations of Cd that cannot occur naturally (Sanità di Toppi and Gabbrielli 1999; Andresen and Küpper 2013). The worldwide mean content of Cd in soils is approximately 0.36 mg kg⁻¹ (Kubier et al. 2019) and, for example, the Czech Republic has set preventive limits of Cd for agricultural soils at 0.4 mg kg⁻¹ for light soils and 0.5 mg kg⁻¹ for regular soils (Vácha et al. 2014). Nonetheless, using higher concentrations in a laboratory setting is still highly relevant for short-term exposure studies to induce symptoms of Cd toxicity.

The potential effect of different Cd salt type treatments has been previously studied. For example, in *Noccaea praecox*, a

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potent Cd/Zn hyperaccumulator, CdCl₂ exposure led to preferential sequestration of Cd into vacuoles in mesophyll cells, whereas CdSO₄ treatment resulted in more Cd binding within the apoplast. However, both Cd salts had a similar effect on the Cd uptake, and overall plant fitness was comparable (Koren et al. 2013). A comparison of Cd(NO₃)₂ and CdCl₂ solutions on fava bean (*Vicia faba*) showed that nitrate salt-treated plants had a thicker root diameter compared to the CdCl₂ treatment under the highest concentration used (300 mg L⁻¹) and higher Cd accumulation in roots under certain tested concentrations (50 and 150 mg L⁻¹) (Piršelová and Ondrušková 2021). Ozkutlu et al. (2007) observed that immersion of durum wheat flag leaves in a Cd-containing solution (8.8 mM) with added NaCl promoted Cd accumulation in wheat grains. However, the NaCl-promoted accumulation effect was less pronounced for cadmium sulfate compared to chloride (Cl⁻) or nitrate (NO₃⁻) salts (Ozkutlu et al. 2007).

Nevertheless, these studies used high concentrations of Cd salts, introducing significant levels of accompanying anions (e.g., SO₄²⁻, Cl⁻) into the nutrient medium. These added anions substantially alter the medium's composition, an effect unaccounted for in the experimental designs. In experiments using nutrient-depleted media, this influence was likely even amplified, making the concentration of accompanying anion a key factor responsible for observed differences in these studies (Ozkutlu et al. 2007; Koren et al. 2013; Piršelová and Ondrušková 2021). Elevated levels of Cl⁻ have been shown to enhance Cd uptake, possibly due to (i) enhanced diffusion of Cd²⁺ by Cl⁻ to uptake sites and (ii) phytoavailability of Cl⁻ complexes for potential uptake to the root (Smolders and McLaughlin 1998a, 1996b; McLaughlin et al. 1997; Smolders et al. 1998). For example, CdCl⁺ complexes may be transported by monovalent ion channels, and CdCl₂^o complexes may diffuse passively through the plasma membrane (Sterckeman and Thomine 2020). In rice, the application of Cl⁻ increased Cd soil availability, upregulated the expression of transporters capable of Cd transport, and promoted Cd root-to-shoot uptake (Guo et al. 2022; Guo et al. 2024).

Sulfate (SO₄²⁻) has also been shown to influence Cd uptake. McLaughlin et al. suggested that CdSO₄^o complexes are taken up by roots with the same efficiency as free Cd²⁺ ions (McLaughlin et al. 1998a; McLaughlin et al. 1998b). However, the effects of SO₄²⁻ appear to be more species-specific. For instance, SO₄²⁻ excess reduced Cd uptake and tissue accumulation in maize (Adhikari et al. 2018), while in wheat, SO₄²⁻ application increased growth and grain yield while reducing Cd concentrations in grains without lowering Cd bioavailability (Shi et al. 2020). Species-specific effects of SO₄²⁻ supplementation in alleviating Cd toxicity were also observed in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and *Nicotiana tabacum* (Lyčka et al. 2023).

Our preliminary experiments revealed differences in the root morphology of 7-day-old *A. thaliana* seedlings grown on media containing two different Cd salts. Roots growing on a medium with 50 μM of CdSO₄ were visually shorter than those germinating on the CdCl₂ medium. Therefore, we aimed to elucidate the differing effects of CdSO₄ and CdCl₂ salts on *A. thaliana* development.

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Plant Material and Growth Conditions

Seeds of *A. thaliana* [ecotypes Columbia-0 (Col), Landsberg erecta (Ler), and Wassilewskija (Ws)] were obtained from

Nottingham Arabidopsis Stock Centre, United Kingdom. Seeds were surface-sterilized by ethanol and germinated on half-strength Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium (Duchefa Biochemicals; M0255) with 0.8% plant agar (Duchefa Biochemicals; P1001) under short-day conditions (8 h light (100 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹), 21°C and 16 h dark, 19°C) for 7 days in growth unit (Photon Systems Instruments).

Seeds of *N. tabacum* were obtained from Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, London, United Kingdom. Seeds were surface-sterilized with 90% bleach (SAVO Original) and germinated on full-strength MS medium with 1% sucrose and 0.8% plant agar under short-day conditions for 16 days in growth unit (Photon Systems Instruments).

MS medium was spiked with 0.1 M stock solutions of CdCl₂ (Sigma Aldrich) or CdSO₄ (Carl Roth) to achieve final concentrations of 4 or 50 μM of both salts, respectively. The lower concentration of Cd salts was selected based on preventive limits for agricultural soils in the Czech Republic (Vácha et al. 2014). Compensation for Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻ supplement was done by K₂SO₄ (Penta Chemicals) in CdCl₂ treatment and by KCl (Penta Chemicals) in CdSO₄ treatment.

Seedlings were collected as whole or divided into root and shoot parts, and stored at -80°C.

2.2 | Root Measurement

Seedlings were photographed and root lengths were analyzed using RootDetection v0.1.2 software (<http://www.labutils.de/rd.html>). The pixel length was recalculated to millimetres by a defined scale in the photographs. Statistical analysis was calculated by the Kruskal-Wallis test with the post-hoc Dunn test (Bonferroni-corrected, $p < 0.05$).

2.3 | Proteomic Analysis of *A. thaliana* Seedlings

Protein extraction and solubilization of frozen root samples were done with 50 μL of hot SDT buffer (4% SDS, 100 mM DTT; 100 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.6) and glass beads and vortexing at max speed for 30 s. Samples were incubated in Thermo Mixer C (Eppendorf) at 95°C for 1 h and 2000 rpm. After centrifugation at room temperature for 15 min and 14 000 g, 20 μL of supernatant were collected. The remaining material was mixed with another 200 μL of hot SDT buffer and incubated at 95°C for 1 h and 2000 rpm. Afterward, samples were mechanically ground with Teflon homogenizer and glass tube with following incubation at 95°C for 1 h and 2000 rpm. After centrifugation at room temperature for 15 min and 14 000 g, an additional 200 μL of supernatant were collected to a total volume of 220 μL.

Frozen shoot samples were powdered using mortar and pestle in liquid nitrogen, homogenized with glass beads in 100 μL of hot SDT lysis buffer, and incubated at 95°C for 1 h and 2000 rpm. After centrifugation at room temperature for 30 min and 20 000 g, 50 μL of the supernatant were collected.

Half of the solubilized protein mixture was processed by filter-aided sample preparation using Microcon-30kDa centrifugal filters (MRCF0R030; Merck). It included protein reduction and alkylation step using iodoacetamide and subsequent incubation with trypsin (18 h, 37°C). The resulting peptides were extracted into 15 μL of the

final solution. The peptide mixture was cleaned-up using the ethylacetate extraction step. LC-MS/MS analyses were done using nanoElute® (Bruker) connected online to the timsTOF Pro system (Bruker). LC-MS analyses used 60-min-long linear LC gradient, and MS and MS/MS spectra were recorded in the time of flight (TOF) analyzer. All peptide mixtures were analyzed separately using about ~500 ng of the final peptide mixture for analyses of all samples. LC-MS data were processed by MaxQuant software (Cox and Mann 2008) (version 1.6.17.0) with a built-in Andromeda search engine (Cox et al. 2011) and using default settings unless noted otherwise (parameter file generated by MaxQuant software can be found as part of the data upload). Data were searched against UniProt *A. thaliana* proteome and the cRAP contaminant database (version 181122). Match between runs (MBR) was enabled with 0.5 min matching time window set to improve peptide matching accuracy. Only peptide and protein identifications with FDR < 1% were considered. The sum of unique+razor peptides was used for quantitation (Intensity columns in the proteinGroups.txt report file), with a minimum of 1 razor+unique peptide required and 0 minimal number of unique peptides. LoessF data normalization on the protein group intensities columns across all samples was done before further data evaluation. During data post-processing, one root sample from the CdSO₄ treatment was eliminated from the analysis, while for other groups, 6 samples (biological replicas) were analyzed.

Proteins that did not have at least 3 valid values in groups treated with Cd salts were not considered as quantified. Missing values in the normalized log₂-transformed intensity matrix were imputed by the impute.mi function from the 'imp4p' R package (Gianetto 2021) with default setting and specified conditions and biological replicates. Groups were compared by pairwise moderated *t*-tests (BH-corrected, *p* < 0.05) based on Bioconductor 'limma' R package (Ritchie et al. 2015) using the 'MKMisc' R package (Kohl 2022). PCA analysis was done using the 'FactoMineR' R package (Lê et al. 2008). GO enrichment analysis was done by g:Profiler (Raudvere et al. 2019) (<https://biit.cs.ut.ee/gprofiler>) with the exclusion of electronic GO annotations, and the number of terms was reduced based on results from Revigo (Supek et al. 2011) (<http://revigo.irb.hr/>) with the default setting. Functional protein association networks were built by the STRING database (Szklarczyk et al. 2019) (version 11.5, <https://string-db.org/>). Pre-processed proteomic data and analyzed data for both tissues are listed in Tables S1 and S2.

2.4 | Measurement of Metal Content

25 mg of fresh-weight frozen tissue (shoot or root), or 50 mg of whole seedlings were mineralized with 500 µL of concentrated trace metal grade HNO₃ (A509-P500; Fischer Chemical) for 4 days at 60°C with constant shaking on the maximum (100) setting (BFED 53; Binder GmbH). Mineralized samples were diluted with deionized water to a final HNO₃ content of 5% (v/v) and measured by ICP-MS (7900 ICP-MS; Agilent). Collision cell (He mode) with standard tuning using the Agilent tuning solution was used. Metals (²⁴Mg, ³⁹K, ⁴⁴Ca, ⁵⁵Mn, ⁵⁶Fe, ⁶³Cu, ⁶⁶Zn, ⁹⁵Mo, ¹¹¹Cd) were quantified based on the standard curves from the analysis of a 26-element standard (AN9090MN-100; ANALYTIKA). Agilent Mass Hunter software (Agilent) in full quantitative data analysis mode was used to process the acquired data. Statistical analysis was

calculated by the one-way aligned rank transform analysis of variance (ART ANOVA) post hoc test using the ART-C (Elkin et al. 2021) procedure (FDR-corrected, *p* < 0.05) implementing ARTool R package (Wobbrock et al. 2011).

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Sulfate as Accompanying Anion in Cd Salt Causes Stronger Root Growth Inhibition Than Chloride Under High Cd Exposure in *A. thaliana*

To validate our initial hypothesis that CdSO₄ has stronger inhibitory effect on root development compared to CdCl₂, we cultivated three different *A. thaliana* ecotypes for 7 days under relatively low but environmentally relevant concentration of Cd salts (4 µM) and high Cd salt concentration (50 µM) (Figure 1) and the length of roots was evaluated. Ws ecotype showed a difference in root lengths between Cd salt treatments already under low Cd stress, while the effect was absent in the other two ecotypes. Low CdSO₄ stress stimulated root growth in ecotype Col, while both Cd salts in low concentration inhibited root growth in ecotype Ler. High Cd treatment in all three ecotypes adversely affected root growth with significantly more potent inhibition by CdSO₄.

Half-strength MS medium contains 2.99 mM of Cl⁻ and 0.815 mM of SO₄²⁻ (based on MS medium composition from Duchefa Biochemicals; M0255). Adding 50 µM CdCl₂ to the medium represents a 3.34% increase of Cl⁻, and adding 50 µM CdSO₄ increases SO₄²⁻ content by 6.13%. These increments seem relatively minor to explain observed differences between Cd salt treatments. Nevertheless, as the changes between CdCl₂ and CdSO₄ treatments may correspond to the increased concentrations of respective anions, we tested the addition of 100 µM KCl to 50 µM CdSO₄ treatment and 50 µM K₂SO₄ to 50 µM CdCl₂ treatment to compensate for the increased anion in the opposite Cd treatment. The compensation did not show any effect (Figure S1). Therefore, the observed changes were probably connected with the speciation of the respective salt in the MS medium, as Cd could exist in the MS medium in various chemical forms, similarly to the soil solution (Kubier et al. 2019). This could further affect the Cd phytoavailability as well as plant Cd uptake/transport.

To test whether other plants also respond differently to the exposure to different cadmium salts during germination, we cultivated *N. tabacum* seedlings for 16 days— as tobacco root development is slower compared to *A. thaliana*—under low concentration of Cd salts (4 µM), and high Cd salt concentration (50 µM) (Figure S2). *N. tabacum* root lengths remained unchanged under the low Cd treatment. High Cd treatments inhibited root growth more mildly than observed in *A. thaliana* ecotypes (Figure 1), and effect of Cd salt was not detected. Therefore, it can be speculated that the different effects of Cd salts on early plant development are not universal in plants. Nevertheless, it is not excluded, that during prolonged cultivation of *N. tabacum*, differences in development may be observed.

3.2 | CdSO₄ Treatment Has More Detrimental Effect on *A. thaliana* Proteome Compared to Chloride Salt

We were interested if differences in root growth of *A. thaliana* seedlings exposed to different Cd salts will be reflected at the

FIGURE 1 | Root lengths of 7-day-old seedlings of *Arabidopsis thaliana* ecotypes exposed to Cd salts. (A) Root lengths of the ecotype Col-0. (B) Root lengths of the ecotype Ler. (C) Root lengths of the ecotype Ws. Different letters indicate significant differences between treatments calculated by the Kruskal–Wallis test with the post-hoc Dunn test (Bonferroni-corrected, $p < 0.05$). Six agar plates were used for each treatment. n , number of measured roots. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

FIGURE 2 | Differently abundant proteins in the root of *Arabidopsis thaliana* ecotype Col-0 exposed to Cd salts. (A) PCA based on the profile of proteins that were differentially abundant in Cd treatments compared to the control group ($\text{adj.}p < 0.05$, > 2.0 -fold change). (B) Comparison of proteins in Cd treatments that were upregulated compared to the control group ($\text{adj.}p < 0.05$, > 2.0 -fold change) visualized in Venn diagram. (C) Comparison of proteins in Cd treatments that were downregulated compared to the control group ($\text{adj.}p < 0.05$, > 2.0 -fold change) visualized in Venn diagram. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

FIGURE 3 | Comparison of selected proteins in the root of *Arabidopsis thaliana* ecotype Col-0 that were differentially abundant between Cd salt treatments and deregulated compared to control. GO and KEGG pathway enrichment analysis of proteins differentially abundant between Cd treatments that were upregulated (A) or downregulated (B) compared to the control group. Volcano plot visualization of the protein levels in CdCl₂ versus CdSO₄ treatments for upregulated (C) or downregulated (D) proteins compared to control group. Log₂ FC threshold was set to 1.0 and adj.p value threshold to 0.05. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

level of protein composition (for root lengths of seedlings taken for analysis, see Figure S3). To make the analysis more precise, shoot and root parts of the seedlings were analyzed separately. Proteome analysis of shoot tissue extracts (Table S1) did not find any significant difference between Cd salt treatments ($\text{adj.}p < 0.05$). Proteome analysis of root extracts from *A. thaliana* ecotype Col seedlings exposed to 50 μM of Cd salts provided the identification of 5976 proteins and quantification of 5442 proteins (Table S2). Evaluation by pairwise moderated *t*-tests and subsequent application of a 2.0-fold threshold filter revealed 1111 differentially abundant proteins in Cd treatments compared to the control group. These proteins were selected for further analysis. Principal component analysis (PCA) explained 70.3% of the variability in the first two components and distinctively separated proteomes to control, CdCl₂ and CdSO₄ groups (Figure 2A). CdSO₄ treatment had a higher impact on the plant proteome, as evident from the Venn diagrams (Figure 2B,C). The upregulated proteins that were also differentially abundant

between Cd treatments (79 proteins; Figure 2B) were mainly connected to responses to different stimuli based on gene ontology (GO) enrichment (Figure 3A). Downregulated proteins (compared to the control group) that accumulated differentially between Cd treatments (23 proteins; Figure 2C) impacted metabolic pathways connected with the synthesis of secondary metabolites, including GLS biosynthesis and flavonoid biosynthesis (Figure 3B). In both cases, CdSO₄ impacted the changes in protein abundance more profoundly in proteins whose abundance increased upon treatment with either Cd salt as compared to untreated control (Figure 3C). Proteins whose abundance decreased upon treatment with Cd salts were more mildly affected by CdCl₂ as opposed to CdSO₄ (Figure 3D).

Only 7 proteins were specifically upregulated relative to the control group following CdCl₂ treatment and were also differentially abundant compared to CdSO₄ treatment (Figure 2B),

TABLE 1 | Specifically deregulated proteins (compared to the control group) in CdCl₂ treatment that also showed different abundance to CdSO₄ treatment.

Description	Description	logFC (CdCl ₂ -CTR)	logFC (CdSO ₄ -CTR)
Upregulated in CdCl ₂ treatment compared to control treatment			
Structural maintenance of chromosomes protein 3	Q56YN8	1.87	0.75
YTH domain-containing protein ECT4	A0A1P8AS03	1.16	0.04
Phosphoglycerate mutase-like protein	Q8GY96	1.28	-0.04
60S ribosomal protein L10a-3	P59231	1.40	-0.20
Peroxidase 11	Q96519	2.29	-0.27
Probable xyloglucan glycosyltransferase 6	Q9SRT3	1.38	0.07
Probable methyltransferase PMT16	O80844	1.65	0.42
Downregulated in CdCl ₂ treatment compared to control treatment			
Assimilatory sulfite reductase (ferredoxin)	Q9LZ66	-1.28	-0.77
Thiol protease aleurain	Q8H166	-1.14	-0.47
Glutamate dehydrogenase 1	Q43314	-1.43	-0.82
Inhibitor I9 domain-containing protein	Q9C8W7	-1.13	-0.71
Probable desiccation-related protein LEA14	O03983	-1.54	-0.79
Uncharacterized protein At2g38710	Q9ZVJ2	-1.04	-0.29
D-glycerate 3-kinase	Q944I4	-1.18	0.02
Beta-glucosidase 32	Q9FLU8	-1.18	-0.10
Ras-related protein RABA5a	Q9FGK5	-2.23	0.30
Glutathione S-transferase U17	Q9FUS8	-1.77	-0.75
Peroxidase 51	Q9SZE7	-1.86	-0.66
Calcineurin B-like protein 3	Q8LEM7	-1.18	-0.50
Xyloglucan endotransglucosylase/hydrolase protein 24	P24806	-1.50	1.44
Glucan endo-1,3-beta-D-glucosidase	Q8VY12	-2.88	-0.95
Early nodulin-like protein 2	Q9T076	-1.17	-0.35
NDR1/HIN1-like protein 10	Q9SJ52	-1.16	0.80
Nudix hydrolase 25	Q9C6Z2	-1.13	-0.10
Clathrin light chain 3	F4J5M9	-1.08	0.02
Alanine--glyoxylate aminotransferase 2 homolog 3	Q9SR86	-1.53	1.49
Purple acid phosphatase 15	Q9SFU3	-1.85	-0.12
21.7 kDa class VI heat shock protein	Q9FIT9	-1.97	-0.44
Ribonuclease T(2)	F4HUG9	-2.90	-0.05
K-stimulated pyrophosphate-energized sodium pump protein	F4JXE8	-2.36	-0.92

whereas 23 proteins also differentially abundant compared to CdSO₄ treatment were decreased in abundance compared to the control group (Figure 2C). However, these proteins (Table 1) were neither associated with each other based on functional association network analysis using STRING, nor showed any significant functional enrichment (not shown). Analysis of specifically accumulated proteins in the CdSO₄ treatment, relative to control, that were also differentially abundant compared to the CdCl₂ treatment (67 proteins, Figure 2B) showed at least 10 proteins associated with peroxisome (Figure 4). These included CAT1, an isoform of catalase, which is one of the antioxidant enzymes dealing with increased ROS levels due to Cd stress. A previous study showed an increased abundance

of CAT1 in the leaves of *A. thaliana* plants exposed to Cd (Zawoznik et al. 2007). Interestingly, *CAT1* gene expression seems to be mainly connected with pollen and seeds (Mhamdi et al. 2010). However, a higher stress-related abundance of CAT1 supports the hypothesis of Yang et al. (2019) that while CAT2 is important for basal H₂O₂ processing, CAT1 and CAT3 may serve as 'backup' or stress-specific isoforms (Yang et al. 2019). Two H₂O₂-generating glycolate oxidases (GOX), GOX1 and GOX3, were highly abundant in the CdSO₄ treatment. It was previously reported that GOX activity increased in *A. thaliana* seedlings due to Cd exposure (Piacentini et al. 2020). This is complementary with observation in *G. max* where GOX activity was increased in crude root extracts after

FIGURE 4 | Functional association networks of specifically upregulated proteins in CdSO₄ treatment, relative to control, that were differentially abundant compared to the CdCl₂ treatment. Disconnected nodes are hidden from the network. Colored network edges indicate different types of interaction evidence. Node colors correspond to different GO functional enrichment. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

6 days of Cd exposure (Pérez-Chaca et al. 2014). GOX1, GOX3 as well as two other specifically upregulated proteins—pyrimidine 4 (PYD4) and alanine:glyoxylate aminotransferase (AGT)—are involved in photorespiration, an essential metabolic process in leaves. It should be noted that in our experimental setup, roots were grown under light exposure, and collected roots included parts very close to the hypocotyl junction. The basal area near the hypocotyl junction was previously observed to accumulate Chl, despite Chl development being suppressed in roots even under light conditions (Kobayashi et al. 2012). Therefore, the detection of proteins related to photosynthesis or photorespiration that were observed within the root dataset (Table S2) is hardly surprising. Moreover, photorespiratory enzymes were abundant in root

transcriptomes and proteome datasets, pointing to their function in this heterotrophic plant organ (Nunes-Nesi et al. 2014). The increased abundance of proteins belonging to GO terms ‘response to toxic substance’ and ‘response to chemical’ (Figure 4), as well as other stimuli response terms, indicated the elevated stress faced by *A. thaliana* when treated with CdSO₄.

3.3 | Proteomic Data Point to Inhibition of Cellulose Biosynthesis as Factor of Stronger Cd Toxicity Response of CdSO₄

Analysis of specifically downregulated proteins upon CdSO₄ treatment, relative to control, that were also differentially abundant

FIGURE 5 | Functional association networks of specifically downregulated proteins in CdSO₄ treatment, relative to control, that were differentially abundant compared to the CdCl₂ treatment. Disconnected nodes are hidden from the network. Colored network edges indicate different types of interaction evidence. Node colors correspond to different functional enrichment (GO or UniProt). [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

compared to CdCl₂ treatment (100 proteins, Figure 2C) provided a better insight into the effect of CdSO₄ (Figure 5).

One cluster pointed to the inhibition of primary cell wall synthesis. Specifically, components of the cellulose synthase (CESA) complex associated with primary cell wall cellulose deposition (CESA1, CESA6 and CESA3/CEV1) (Persson et al. 2007) had lower abundance. Similarly, glycosyl hydrolase 9A1 (GH9A1/KOR1) and CESA interactive protein 1 (CS11)

were also downregulated. GH9A1 was previously reported to be tightly connected with the CESA complex, suggesting that its endoglucanase activity was important in cellulose synthesis (Lei et al. 2014). The *A. thaliana* mutant, *jiaoyao1*, with a missense mutation in GH9A1, was defective in cell expansion and had disorganized microtubules and cellulose microfibrils (Lei et al. 2014). CESA complex function is tightly connected with cortical microtubules as the movement of CESA complex

FIGURE 6 | Cadmium concentration in 7-day-old seedlings of *Arabidopsis thaliana* ecotype Col-0 exposed to Cd salts in whole seedlings, shoot, and root. Different letters indicate significant differences between treatments calculated by the one-way aligned rank transform analysis of variance (ART ANOVA) post hoc test using the ART-C procedure (FDR-corrected, $p < 0.05$). [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

was found to coincide with them (Paredes et al. 2006). CSII, a microtubule-associated protein with a crucial role in their stability, provides the bridge between the CESA complex and microtubules (Bringmann et al. 2012; Li et al. 2012; Mei et al. 2012). Other proteins associated with the GO term of ‘microtubule cytoskeleton organization’ were also found in lower abundance, like rho-related protein from plants 2 (ROP2), which acts as a positive regulatory switch in tip growth (Jones et al. 2002). Therefore, dysregulation of microtubule organization and cellulose deposition can be suspected to be one of the reasons behind root growth inhibition.

Functional enrichment of Uniprot annotated keywords showed that CdSO₄ treatment negatively influenced sterol and lipid biosynthesis. Another negative effect was observed on L-fucose biosynthesis. Here, GDP-D-mannose 4,6-dehydratase 1 (GMD1) and GDP-4-keto-6-deoxymannose-3,5-epimerase-4-reductase 1 (GER1/FX) had significantly lower abundance. L-fucose is essential in the formation of several cell wall polymers and for protein posttranslational modifications (Reiter et al. 1993; Bi et al. 2023). Inhibition of fucosylation of cell wall polysaccharides was previously reported to suppress root elongation (Villalobos et al. 2015; Dumont et al. 2015).

At least six proteins associated with ribosome biogenesis were present in another cluster of proteins with decreased abundance. Specifically, these included At3g22660 (homolog of yeast EBP2 with an essential role in ribosomal large subunit biogenesis (Wan et al. 2015; Huang et al. 2018)), At1g08410 (homolog of yeast large subunit GTPase 1 (LSG1), that is, involved in the maturation of the large ribosomal subunit in *A. thaliana* (Zhao et al. 2015)), and nuclear/nucleolar GTPase 2 (NUG2/AtNug2), which also plays a role in pre-60S

ribosomal subunit maturation (Im et al. 2011). Another un-highlighted protein within the cluster, embryo sac development arrest 25 (EDA25/SWA2), was also found to have a potential role in ribosome biogenesis in *A. thaliana* (Li et al. 2009). Its protein homolog in yeast is involved in ribosome maturation and transport (Milkereit et al. 2001).

Varying root proteome profiles between Cd salt treatments may reflect a stronger Cd stress when seedlings were exposed to CdSO₄ due to the potentially higher Cd uptake compared to the CdCl₂ treatment. Another possible explanation, complementary to the previous hypothesis, would be that CdCl₂ and CdSO₄ treatments lead to a different spatial distribution of Cd on tissue and/or cellular levels, triggering distinct plant responses.

3.4 | Sulfate as Accompanying Anion Enhances Cd Plant Uptake and Accumulation in Shoot

To address whether the observed changes in *Arabidopsis* phenotypes and proteomes between the different Cd uptake, we analyzed ionomes of treated plants (Figure 6 and Table S2). Plants exposed to CdSO₄ had higher concentrations of Cd in shoot and whole seedlings compared to those treated with CdCl₂, while Cd levels in the root were the same (Figure 6). The elevated levels of Cd in whole seedlings pointed to increased uptake of Cd in plants treated with sulfate salt. This higher uptake of Cd resulted in Cd accumulation in the shoot (Figure 6). The lack of Cd retention in the root indicates a dysregulation of defense mechanisms that help to sequester Cd, leading to increased root-to-shoot translocation. This phenomenon might be linked not only to changes in the cell wall's Cd-binding capacity—a key mechanism for mitigating Cd toxicity—but also to the chelation of Cd by organic ligands such as phytochelatins (PCs), its vacuolar compartmentalization, or other mechanisms that can prevent Cd penetration into xylem vessels, thereby enhancing its root-to-shoot translocation (Kosakivska et al. 2021).

Cd treatment, irrespective of the type of Cd salt, led to decreased levels of Mn, Zn and Fe in whole seedlings and roots, while the Zn content was also lower in shoots (Table S3). These changes are unsurprising given the Cd uptake and translocation dependence on transporters involved in the transport of other metals such as Fe, Mn or Zn (Qin et al. 2020). Contrastingly, Mo levels were elevated in whole seedlings compared to control (Table S3). Despite the difference in Cd levels between Cd salt treatments, the concentrations of other metals remained unchanged (Table S3). In our previous study, analyzing the consequences of long-term exposure of *A. thaliana* plants to low Cd salt concentration (Lyčka et al. 2023), intracellular levels of Mg, K, Ca and Cu were significantly affected. Our results could indicate that a 7-day exposure period may not be sufficient to detect subtle ionic changes induced by relatively high doses of Cd salts, or that levels of these metals are stable under these experimental conditions.

Here, we demonstrated that *A. thaliana* root development was more stunted under CdSO₄ than CdCl₂ treatment, with higher Cd uptake and allocation to shoot in plants exposed to the sulfate salt. These effects were independent of SO₄²⁻ or Cl⁻ concentrations, as supplementing these ions did not mitigate the inhibitory effect on root growth. Proteomic analysis revealed that CdSO₄ had a more profound impact

on the proteome than CdCl₂, particularly affecting proteins involved in microtubule organization and primary cell wall synthesis. Given the end-point nature of our study, the observed changes likely reflect a response to heightened Cd toxicity under CdSO₄ treatment, rather than the first piece of domino toppling the plant's defenses and leading to easier Cd penetration and accumulation. These changes are likely related to the formation of complexes between Cd²⁺ and anions and their ability to be taken up by roots. Overall, our study highlights the often-overlooked role of accompanying anions in modulating the toxicity of cationic pollutants. These findings are particularly important for the design of short-term studies utilizing high doses of chemicals to induce observable stress responses to heavy metals.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in ProteomeXchange Consortium at <https://www.proteomexchange.org/>, reference number PXD062135.

The liquid chromatography, tandem mass spectrometry proteomics data have been deposited to the ProteomeXchange Consortium via the PRIDE partner repository with the dataset identifier PXD062135.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Fig. S1: Root lengths of 7-day-old seedlings of *A. thaliana* ecotype Col exposed to 50 μ M of Cd salts with the compensation of the anion addition. **Fig. S2:** Root lengths of 16-day-old seedlings of *N. tabacum* exposed to Cd salts. **Fig. S3:** Root lengths of seedlings exposed to 50 μ M of Cd salts that were used for proteome analysis. **Table S1:** Proteomic data for shoot. **Table S2:** Proteomic data for root. **Table S3:** Effect of cadmium salts on macro- and micronutrient status of *A. thaliana* in whole seedlings and separate tissues.